

Tuning Musical Instruments using FFT and Python

(Penalaan alatan muzik menggunakan FFT dan Python)

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ABSTRACT

Tuning musical instrument to the same pitch is very important in orchestra or any performance that require more than one musical instrument. However, factors such as the temperature and moisture in the surrounding can affect the tuning of musical instruments. Besides that, long hours and consistent training is important when undergoing ear training and boring musical lesson causing some musicians to easily lose interest when learning. All the issues mentioned above are addressed in this research paper. There are three main objectives in this research, that is building a phone application for the ease of tuning musical instruments, providing ear training and basic music training in a fun and interactive way. The GUI of the phone application is built using Pycharm and kivy. Techniques used in processing the input audio signal are Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and the windowing technique. The type of ear training focused is the ability to distinguish between the notes based on their respective pitch. The ear training is programmed as a game for fun learning. The end results are the GUI of the tuning application being able to display frequency, note names and the difference between the pitch of the note played with the correct pitch of that particular note. The tuner has a reasonably fast time execution.

Keywords: Tuning musical instruments; FFT; ear training; phone application; Python

ABSTRAK

Penalaan alat muzik ke pic yang sama adalah penting dalam orkestra atau persembahan yang menggunakan lebih daripada satu alat muzik. Namun begitu, faktor seperti suhu dan kelembapan sekeliling membuatkan alat muzik tidak dapat ditala dengan baik. Selain itu, masa latihan yang panjang dan konsisten amat diperlukan semasa menjalankan latihan telinga dan sesetengah pemuzik mudah hilang minat terhadap pembelajaran alat muzik. Kajian ini adalah untuk mengatasi isu-isu yang disebutkan. Tiga objektif utama ditetapkan iaitu membina aplikasi telefon untuk memudahkan penalaan pic alat muzik, memberikan latihan telinga dan latihan muzik asas dalam cara yang menarik dan interaktif. GUI aplikasi penalaan alat muzik dibina menggunakan Pycharm dan kivy. Teknik pemprosesan isyarat audio yang digunakan dalam kajian ini ialah Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) dan teknik tettingkap. Latihan telinga yang difokuskan dalam kajian ini ialah kemahiran untuk membezakan not berdasarkan pic dan ia dijalankan dengan cara yang menarik. Dapatan kajian ini ialah GUI aplikasi penalaan alat muzik yang dibina dan dapat memaparkan nilai frekuensi, nama not muzik dan perbezaan antara not yang dimainkan dengan not tepat. Penalaan ini mempunyai peleraian masa yang agak pantas..

Kata Kunci: Penalaan alat muzik; FFT; latihan telinga; aplikasi telefon; Python

INTRODUCTION

Tuning musical instrument is an important basic skill for all musicians. Tuning is a method that is done by matching pitch of a musical instrument to the desired pitch. In general, the standard pitch to tune to is note A above middle C, which means tuning to where note A4 which is equal to 440Hz. The standard pitch is also known as “concert pitch” which is also used by orchestras. Musical instruments go out of tune easily due to

temperature and humidity changes of the surrounding. Thus, tuning before a performance is a must for orchestras to avoid the difference in pitch from affecting the performance.

Ear training is also basic training for musicians. However, ear training is usually exhausting because it requires long hours and consistent training. This can cause difficulties and make some musicians lose interest in training. Thus, this research aims to solve the issues mentioned by building a phone application that is

capable of tuning musical instruments, provide ear training and provide basic training in a fun and interactive way.

The tuning system used in this study is equal temperament, in which one octave contains twelve equal size semitones with a 2:1 ratio. According to Figure 1, one octave contains twelve notes: C#, D, D#, E, F, F#, G, G#, A, A#, and B. Every semitone has a ratio of $2^{1/12}$ and is the difference in frequency between two pitch. An overtone is a tone in harmonic series and its frequency is twice that of the fundamental tone. Ear training or aural skills is the ability to differentiate pitches, melodies, chords, intervals, and rhythms only by hearing. For the tuning application to understand pitch, MIDI is used. MIDI or Musical Instrument Digital Interface is the communication protocol to send instrument digital data. It is also used by computers and electronic keyboards.

component of the signal whereas side lobes approach zero at intervals of $\Delta f = \frac{F_s}{N}i$ at both sides of the main lobe. After windowing a signal, the signal's frequency resolution is determined by the width of the main lobe. Narrow main lobes gives smaller frequency resolution and precision in distinguishing frequency that are near to each other in value. However, narrow main lobes can contribute to spectral leakage to the side lobes as well. Thus, choosing a window function that gives a good frequency resolution and spectral leakage suppression is important. In this study, Hann window is chosen because of the reasonable frequency resolution. (Michael Cerna et al. 2000)

Notes	Prime		Second		Third	Fourth		Fifth		Sixth		Seventh
Natural	C		D		E	F		G		A		B
Sharp		C#		D#			F#		G#		A#	
Flat		Db		Eb			Gb		Ab		Bb	
Latin	Do		Re		Mi	Fa		Sol		La		Si
Frequency (Hz)	261.63	277.18	293.66	311.13	329.63	349.23	369.99	392.00	415.30	440.00	466.16	493.88
Scale step	$\sqrt[12]{2}$											
Distance in semitones	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Distance in cents	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
----- 1 Octave = 12 Semitones = 1200 Cents -----												

Figure 1. Notes, frequencies and symbols in C major scale
Source: Music Acoustics UNSW 1997

When sampling analogue signals to digital signals, spectral leakage is very likely to occur. Spectral leakage happens when the signal's time record has a nonintegral number of cycles. This is because the FFT algorithm is assumed to be taking samples so that the time recorded is exactly repeated and the signal in the time record are periodic at intervals throughout the length of time record. (Michael Cerna et al. 2000) Spectral leakage causes distortion in measurement by spreading the energy from a frequency component over to adjacent frequency bins. To reduce the effect of spectral leakage, the input signal is convoluted with a window function.

A window has a continuous spectrum that comprise of a main lobe and a few side lobes. The main lobe is concentrated at each frequency

The musical instruments chosen for testing in this research are Chinese flute Dizi and Xiao. Dizi is a transverse flute and is made from bamboo. It has six finger holes that produce tone, a blow hole and a membrane hole. Aloe vera membrane is pasted on the membrane hole and produces sound caused by the flow of air in the flute. Xiao is a end-blow flute which is usually made from black, yellow or white bamboo. It has six finger holes and the top part is covered by the inner layer with a hole carved out at the side. (Lim SK, 2013). Xiao does not have a need for membrane and thus harder for it to go out of tune. Dizi and Xiao can only play in the range of two octaves and major second.

METHODOLOGY

Audio signals from musical instruments are recorded using a microphone and go through the

process of sampling, Hann Windowing, FFT, comparing input with frequency of music notes and finally output as music notes in the mobile application. The following are the main parameters e used:

$$f_{tn} = 69 + 12 \log_2(f/440) \tag{1}$$

$$ntf = 440 * 2^{(n-69)/12} \tag{2}$$

$$ntb = \frac{ntf}{S} \tag{3}$$

where f_{tn} is the frequency to number conversion, ntf the number to frequency conversion and ntb is the note to the corresponding bin and S is the frequency step.

In each FFT frame, 32768 ADC samples are store in array. Then, the samples are multiplied with Hann Window function and frequency information are obtained using FFT. The audio frame are overlapped to get a faster time resolution, then the average frequency spectrum is obtained. From the frequency spectrum, spectrum bin that has the highest amplitude is determined and frequency value is calculated. The frequency value is then compared with the frequency value of the musical notes to determine the musical notes of input signal. (M. Gasior et al. 2004) When the frame per FFT reaches 16 frame, frequency value, musical notes and deviation from the musical note is outputed to the GUI on mobile application. Figure 2 shows the flowchart for the musical instrument tuner.

Ear training is provided in the mobile application in the form of game. Pycharm and kivy are used to build the GUI mobile application for ear training. The ear training aims to train the user in distinguishing the different pitch by playing a game. In the game, a random pitch is sounded and the user has to input the correct answer to win the game. For every round of the game, three chances are given and the user can replay the pitch given as many times as they liked.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The smallest cent deviation that is detected by human is 6 cent. (D.B. Loeffler, 2007) However, there is no established standard to determine the accuracy for a musical instrument. Thus, the standard accuracy for musical instrument is assumed to be 0.05 cent in this research. In this experiment, an electronic tuner is used to sound the specific pitch when the tuner application is turn on. The input from the electronic tuner will be store in a list and the cent deviation is calculated for each output. The function for the accuracy of the tuner is:

$$\text{Cent Deviation} = 12 \log_2 \frac{f_2}{f_1} \tag{4}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum O_s * 100\%}{\sum \text{Sample}} \tag{5}$$

Figure 2. Flowchart for the musical instrument tuner

where f_2 is the frequency output of the mobile application tuner, f_1 is the pitch frequency that is desired and $\sum O_s$ is the total number of output within the set standard. A total of 200 samples were taken in this accuracy test. According to table 1, the accuracy of the notes increases along with the increase in frequency. The accuracy of the tuner is too different for each note and cannot be used as a tuner. The accuracy of the mobile application needs to be improved before it can be used.

Table 1. Accuracy for each note.

Note name	Total number of output within the set standard	Accuracy (%)
C4	8	4
C#4	18	9
D4	14	7
D#4	27	13.5
E4	37	18.5
F4	62	31
F#4	79	39.5
G4	130	65
G#4	117	58.5
A4	142	71
A#4	155	77.5
B4	197	98.5

The parameters for the musical instrument tuner are shown in Table 2.

Table2. Parameter of the musical instrument tuner

Parameter	Value
Sampling frequency	22050 Hz
Frame size	2048
Frame per FFT	16
Sample per FFT	32768
frequency step	0.67291259765625 Hz

The sample calculations are as the following: assuming the frequency value of the input is 278.5858 Hz,

$$n = \text{MIDI representation of notes}$$

$$\text{freq_to_number} = 69 + 12 \log_2(278.5858/440) = 61.0874$$

$$\text{num_to_frequency} = 440 * 2^{(61.0874-69)/12} = 278.5858$$

$$\text{note_to_fftbins} = 61.0874/0.67291259765625 = 98.6717$$

$$n - n_0 = 61.0874 - 61 = 0.874$$

From the above calculation, the notes that are played is:
 Frequency = 278.5858 Hz
 Notes = note C# + 9 cent
 Deviation from the correct pitch = 0.4868

As shown in Figure 3, the output frequency, notes, and the deviation from the correct pitch is the same as in calculation.

Figure 3. GUI of the tuner mobile application

Figure 4 shows the flow chart of the ear training game. The game uses using pyaudio to play the sound the pitch, thus all the pitch were rounded off to the nearest interger because pyaudio is not compatible with string value.

Figure 4. Flowchart of the ear training game

CONCLUSION

The audio signals were processed using Hanning Window and FFT to obtain the frequency value and output it to the GUI with a reasonable time resolution. However, the accuracy of the mobile application tuner was low and therefore had to be improved. The accuracy of the tuner can be improved by removing the white noise from the sampling process. To make it more user friendly, animation of a pitch gauge with deviation of cent can be inserted for easier pitch reading. Lastly, an option for changing the standard pitch can be inserted as well. For the ear training game, it provides ear training for distinguishing between different musical notes. This game is also able to give basic training in a fun and interactive way. It can be improved by adding more training such as distinguishing the intervals, chords, scales and key signatures.

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